

Multimedia Annotation through WebGIS and Mobile Devices: Wireless Infrastructure Project for the UNESCO Site in Cerveteri - Italy

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Abstract

In this paper we present an original integration of technologies. The main objectives of the general project for the UNESCO site of Cerveteri are: solutions that integrate survey techniques and organize data in the GIS - called Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico Ceretano (SITAC) - dedicated to this case study; accessibility and fruition of a complex archaeological area within a continuous intervention process; offer the general public, researchers, and managers an important cognitive base that integrates multimedia and geographic scientific data through remote or on-site interaction with the SITAC. The proposed system is based on the integration of data communication and LBS devices connected in the wireless network with multimedia and multimodal characteristics in the archaeological area. This innovative and powerful solution - called MA(geo)RIS Multimedia Annotation of Geo-Referenced Information Sources - will allow collaborative construction and fruition of annotations made by users on georeferenced information by combining three web-enabled applications: a plug-in annotating multimedia content (MadCow), an environment for multimodal interaction (Chambre), and the WebGIS application (MapServer). The resulting system is unique in its offering a wealth of possibilities for interacting with geographically based material especially where there is a high quantity of resources in a complex site.

Categories and Subject Descriptors (according to ACM CCS): H.5.1 [Multimedia Information Systems]: Hypertext navigation and maps Artificial, Augmented, and virtual realities J.0 [Computer Applications]: General, field sciences J.5 [Arts and Humanities]: Archaeology J.4 [Social and Behavioural Sciences]: H.3.4 [Systems and Software]: Distributed systems

1. Introduction

The combined GIS and WebGIS application, called Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico Ceretano (SITAC) [CMR06], was developed within an integrated project for the UNESCO site in Cerveteri - the Etruscan Necropolis "La Banditaccia" in proximity to the ancient Caere city developed between the 9th and 2nd centuries BC, 40 km from Rome (Italy). The SITAC GIS initiative was created in conformance with the Management Plan approved by UNESCO and it responds to knowledge, planning and management needs, while the general valorization project aims to preserve cultural heritage and promote tourist fruition of the archaeological, natural, and landscape resources of this site. Since May 2006 a light-weight electrical train circuit is the

backbone of accessibility of a large area that contains thousands of tombs and several kms of Etruscan roads. The main objectives of the new project for innovative technologies in the valorisation of the site are: provide a solution that integrates problems relating to the survey; accessibility and fruition of a complex archaeological area in an evolutionary vision of the valorisation procedures; offer the general public, scholars, and managers an important cognitive base that integrates multimedia and geographic scientific data through remote or on-site interaction with the SITAC. The main strategy is to converge data, analysis, and applications into a single computerized geographic system connected to a series of mobile devices that offers users an assisted visit as well as multimedia and multimodal interaction. The system is installed on a centralized web server and includes applications

that provide the various user profiles (tourists, experts, historians, archaeologists) a series of services in remote mode (on-line) as well as direct (on-site): new possibilities for surveys, representations, and research in collaborative mode and for guided fruition of the site tourists.

Figure 1: Architecture overview.

Figure 2: MapServer architecture.

Figure 3: 3D models.

2. The project framework

The workgroup acquired the guidelines and actions proposed in the UNESCO Management Plan for the site and the proposed strategy is centred on the construction of an IT environment with multiple input-output possibilities. We consider four typologies of users: 1) expert users surveying and making annotations for technical purposes: historical analysis, cataloguing, excavation, conservation and restoration plans, risk evaluation; 2) tourist agencies and promoters; 3)

Figure 4: Vertical iconometric views.

Figure 5: The tourist pen based LBS application running on a tablet pc device.

tourists - providing them with interactive and multimedia solutions: mobile devices such as on-site guides, personal tour planning and recording, web services and virtual tours; 4) researchers and students that can use the innovative annotation WebGIS environment, for collaborative and for e-learning purposes. The proposed system is based on the integration of data communication and LBS solutions with multimedia and multimodal characteristics in the archaeological area of "La Banditaccia". A wireless network infrastructure (wi-fi) - that covers the plateau of the necropolis - it will be possi-

Figure 6: The MUST user interface.

ble to further develop the functionality of a series of mobile data acquisition systems and the referencing of geographic and multimedia information collected in the SITAC and published with the WebGIS. The portable instruments in wireless communication with the central server (Figure 1) are diversified in relation to the tourist and technical-scientific users: from the multilingual audio-guide system onboard the electric train, to the palms with GPS, from Tablet-PCs with GIS functions, to Quick Survey Kit equipment. The centralized system enables the web publication of useful tourist and technical-scientific information through a web site with public sections and sections reserved for registered users. The portable systems will be equipped with GPS receivers for automatic position recognition and therefore the proximity to archaeological structures. They will be able to present multimedia material (text, video, audio, images) relative to the actual position of the user. Through portable equipment (Tablet-PCs and Palms) tourists will be able to create personal textual notes, enter sensations and comments, or store photographs and brief audiovisuals associated with the location of the shot. Technical-scientific users can take advantage of more advanced functions of interaction with the SITAC, of interactivity and communication via web, and auxiliary application functions for the various types of surveys in the field. Furthermore, a client-server GIS application is useful to support site surveying, surveillance and security management in terms of risk and vulnerability. The role of the wireless network is to deliver the data exchanged between client applications and servers. The set of server is divided in three main category: MAP, MadCow and HTTP servers. A MAP server create maps for the internet using GIS data from shapefiles, tabfiles, or SDE. Also can utilize data from any database. Can run as CGI or through scripting languages such as Perl, Python, Tk/Tcl, Guile and even Java. In particular, a cartographic view is produced from the overlay of vector and raster layers with symbol legend and scale and orientation indicators. The MAP server publishes the Web version of this material, thus allowing interaction with its visualisation, as well as queries to a database, containing the data and metadata associated with the cartographic layers. Links to multimedia objects can be added as well. Any object is associated with its coordinates with respect to a projection and a geographic reference system. Figure 2 shows the typical structure of a Map server application. The MadCow server [BCL*05] handle all the multimedia annotation aspects. MadCow is a client server application exploiting HTTP to transfer information between a standard Web browser and an annotation server. The server uses a database to store webnotes, which are created by following a typical pattern of interaction: while browsing documents, users identify portions for which they want to create an annotation and open a plugin window in which to specify the annotation content. The user can associate the portion with a new link to a different URL, thus creating an active zone, or with some interactively defined complex content, thus defining a webnote. One or more HTTP server is used for access the WWW.

MAP and MadCow servers can be alternatively located in a remote address and accessed through the HTTP server.

2.1. The SITAC WebGIS application

The SITAC basically integrates iconometric and topographic elements, organized into layers of objects and dataset, for layouts that can be used by archaeologists in direct surveys, but its integration with a web server and an interactive WebGIS application makes it a special multimedia content management system with a geographic attitude. The SITAC shared through the web is a collaborative platform accessible to all participants involved in the different activities concerning the site. Their work on data and documentation can gradually increase the multimedia offer to the tourists and the promoters. This is the ideal progression in order to foster the convergence of various fields of expertise and the implementation of a collaborative web-based platform using GIS and DBMS [BCL*05]. Several thematic layers concerning the Necropolis Area were collected in GIS environment including: topographic and dGPS survey, 3D models (see Figure 3), photo-interpretation of aerial views based on their historical overlay mapping, vertical photogrammetry views (Figure 4), other multimedia documentation (short digital and real movies, audio commentaries and storytelling, video documentation of cultural events). Additional pictures document the interior of the relevant monuments with the aim to build the multimedia georeferenced archive at the basis of the remote visiting web services. In particular the data relationship inside the GIS application between the planimetric and vertical thematic, organized in different views with an innovative technique, allowed for extremely dynamic navigation of SITAC information and for quick organization of useful and understandable visualization output (map/prospect). A synthesis of the SITAC dedicated to the archaeological sites in the Cerveteri has been published on Internet through the implementation of an open-source Map Server. The development of the Map Server within a larger web application foresees both the public side of the website, as a promotional tool for cultural heritage, and intranet side with accounting for technical activities. In addition to the geographic visualisation, this system will further develop the information storing, modification and updating functions in remote mode through portable equipment used directly on the archaeological areas.

2.2. The multimedia annotation system

An innovative and powerful solution - called MA(geo)RIS Multimedia Annotation of Geo-Referenced Information Sources - will allow collaborative construction and fruition of annotations made by users on georeferenced information by combining three web-enabled applications: a plug-in annotating multimedia content (MadCow), an environment for multimodal interaction (Chambre) [BFL*06], and the WebGIS application (MapServer). The resulting system is

unique in its offering a wealth of possibilities for interacting with geographically based material especially where there is a high quantity of resources in a complex site. Interaction with the system occur in different modality and through different devices. We identify two main client application class: Desktop and Location Based System (LBS) applications. Desktop and LBS applications allow the user to operate in a georeferenced environment of multimedia sources with different kind of polices for user interaction. LBS applications use a GPS receiver in order to understand the exact location of the user, while Desktop applications are user location independent. Users of the system are: tourists, tour operator, site maintainers, security agent, students, researchers, teachers, cultural heritage institutions. For example a tourist can interact with the SIT through Desktop application on site (in a multimedia laboratory) or from a generic internet access point by opening the main web page of the SIT. After a login, the tourist user can access to GIS information (obtained from the MAP server) and annotate it (using the MadCow toolbar) in order to create a virtual georeferenced tour of the archaeological site. When the tourist arrive at the archaeological site he can choice between a tablet pc and a pocket pc (devices for tourist LBS applications) in order to be guided by the "virtual path" planned before (see Figure 5). The tourist's detected location is used for automatically guide through the archaeological site, and for obtain multimedia related contents (retrieved by the HTTP server). By annotating the "virtual path" directly on site, one can record text, audio, photos, and locate this media in the georeferenced environment (via MadCow server capability of handle multimedia annotation). When the visit of the archaeological site is finished, the tourist can access the georeferenced annotated path, either via a multimedia support (CD or DVD) either via an internet access point trough the SIT web portal. In a more complex scenario a site maintainers can edit the georeferenced environment either via Desktop either via LBS applications by a dedicated client for the MAP server. Finally the Multilingual Simultaneous Transmission (MUST) subsystem is a combination of hardware and software used for a simultaneous radio transmission of audio tracks. This system is located on board of an electrical train. We have developed this technology in order to guide groups of tourist coming from different nations. The MUST system can operate in two different modalities: manual and LBS. In the MUST's LBS modality the train's location is used to detect the proximity to a particular Point Of Interest (POI). If a POI is considered near the train position (see Figure 6) an audio commentary is transmitted to the user's headphones. Each headphone is carried with a small radio receiver and can be configured for receive a particular radio channel. Different channels are used for different languages. In the MUST's manual modality the selection of the POI is not automatic. In order to help and improve the activities relating to investigation, excavation, monitoring and planning, the operators were given a field survey kit: a set of instruments and procedures for georeferencing, quick surveying and positioning of archaeological

findings or other phenomenon. It contains a digital camera, a GPS and tablet-pc that interact with the central information system. The goal is to gradually create an intelligent map of the site, its intelligence deriving from two factors: the mapping valorises the expertise that collaborated on the site and it was also implemented in a highly interactive network system.

3. Related works

While, to the best of our knowledge there is a lack of specific literature on georeferenced annotation, there are several studies on the individual components of the technologies involved. Annotation systems are becoming widespread, as the interest for enriching available content, both for personal and collaborative use, is increasing. Apart from generic annotation facilities for proprietary format documents, professional users are interested in annotating specific types of content. As an example, AnnoteImage allows the creation and publishing of personal atlases about annotated medical images. In I2Cnet, a dedicated server provides medical annotated images. Video documents can be annotated in dedicated browsers, such as Vannotea or VideoAnnEx. However, these tools are generally not integrated into existing browsers, so that interaction with them disrupts usual navigation over the web. Moreover, they usually deal with a single type of document and do not support the wealth of formats involved in modern web pages. Architectures for multimodal interaction are also becoming available, usually devoted to specific applications, for example in the field of performing arts [SHK03] [IBM] [KM95]. In these cases interaction capabilities are restricted to specific mappings between multimodal input and effects on the rendered material, while Chambre open architecture allows the definition of flexible patterns of interaction, adaptable to different conditions of usage. The field of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) has recently witnessed a growth in the number of web applications, both commercial and open source [PT03]. Among the commercial ones, the most important represent web-based versions of stand-alone applications, usually running on powerful workstations. For example, ArcIMS derives from ArcInfo, MapGuide from Autocad and MapXtreme from MapInfo. In the field of open source solutions, MapServer represents to date the most complete, stable and easy-to-use suite offering a development environment for the construction of Internet applications able to deal with spatial data [Mit05]. The MapServer project is managed by the University of Minnesota which also participates in the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) [OGC03] by setting specifications and recommendations to support interoperable solutions that "geo-enable" the Web, wireless and location-based services. Current developments are focused on the production of front-end for the publication and personalization of HTML pages, starting from .map files. Among these, FIST offers an environment of editing on-line, enabling also non-expert users to exploit features of remote mapping. How-

ever, these environments require that the user possesses writing rights on the original GIS content, or on some private server, while our solution enables the collaborative construction of geo-referenced resources starting from publicly available data offered by existing GISs. See also the recent successful experiences of tourist fruition schemes around excavating areas, where the attraction is not only the archaeological resources but also the technical activity itself, made of intelligent solutions and methodical jobs.

4. Conclusions

We assumed that the different phases, from surveying to tourist exploitation, had to be coordinated and parallel: interventions gradually increase the fruition possibilities of the site and meanwhile the surveying activities employing the networked equipment produce documentation and support the site knowledge. By collecting georeferenced documentation it's possible to offer, on demand, a multimedia description of the localized resources. Fruition of these contents can occur both on-site, through the local wireless infrastructure using the mobile devices, and also through Internet. In order to recognize real-time positions and resources in the area, these devices have to be equipped with Location Based System and connected to web applications oriented to high interactive use. The spatial and geographical dimensions of the information sources on the Web are usually overlooked. The Ma(geo)ris framework strengthens the relation between the information available on the Web and its geographical dimensions, thus allowing interaction between users and georeferenced information published with WebGIS. The annotation system, the WebGIS application, the multimedia and multimodal approach to objects represent the innovative perspective of the presented project. Benefits can be obtained for different activities: remote learning, collaborative enrichment of available resources about cultural heritage, enriched experience while visiting some artistic or archaeological site. Moreover different multimedia sources, whether georeferenced or not, can be connected among them and interacted with exploiting multimodal interfaces, thus supporting also users suffering from sensorial-motor impairments. The question of local expertise is both strategic and transversal to the entire project so e-learning modules are foreseen in the general architecture of the web services. In the field of archaeology GIS has become indispensable because it enables a territorial approach on a variable scale of an environment with complex georeferenced documentation. Now it is only a question of benefiting from the recent growth of geographic culture and interactivity in order to draw new experts and tourists to locations where there is much to discover. The WebGIS has to be conceived as a collaborative platform for research and dissemination producing benefits for the technical and scientific community as well as for the network of cultural promoters and tour operators. Finally, this process can grant the rapid en-

richment of the content base that has to be offered to the public fruition of local resources.

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